

Original article

Assessment of patient satisfaction with nursing care at Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare, Bauchi state, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Patient satisfaction is a vital indicator of healthcare quality and is strongly influenced by nursing care. Limited data exist on patient satisfaction with nursing services in tertiary hospitals in Bauchi State, Nigeria. This study assessed patients' satisfaction with nursing care and examined patients' perceptions of nurses' attitudes and strategies for improvement. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional design was used. From a target population of 370 inpatients admitted for at least three days, 192 participants were selected using convenience sampling. Data were collected with a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire that had been validated for content and demonstrated a test-retest reliability coefficient of 0.78. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were computed. **Results:** The participants were predominantly female (56%) and aged 40–49 years (35%). The aggregated mean score for nurses' attitude was 3.39 (on a 4-point scale), reflecting a positive perception. Overall patient satisfaction with nursing care was 2.90, indicating moderate satisfaction. Items addressing communication, respect, and carefulness scored highest, while doubts about nurses' ability and dissatisfaction with some aspects of care had lower means. Respondents strongly agreed that timely medication administration, adequate staffing, and patient involvement would further improve satisfaction. **Conclusion:** Patients reported moderate satisfaction with nursing care. Although nurses were perceived positively, gaps remain in communication, staff availability, and patient participation in care decisions. Incorporating routine patient feedback and targeted quality improvement initiatives is recommended.

Keywords: Nursing care, Nigeria, Patient satisfaction, Quality of care, Teaching hospital

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Introduction

Patient satisfaction is defined as the degree of congruence between patients' expectations of healthcare and their actual experience of the services received.¹ It is now recognised as a core component of healthcare quality, influencing treatment adherence, return visits, and overall health outcomes.² Because nurses provide the majority of direct bedside care, nursing care is a principal driver of overall patient satisfaction.³ Multiple factors shape satisfaction with nursing care, including the quality of interpersonal communication, responsiveness to patient needs, respect for privacy, and perceived clinical

competence.⁴ When patients feel that nurses listen attentively, explain procedures clearly, and involve them in decision-making, satisfaction increases substantially.⁵ Conversely, inadequate staffing, hurried interactions, and poor communication are consistently associated with lower satisfaction ratings.⁶

In low- and middle-income countries, patient satisfaction with nursing services often falls below desired levels due to resource constraints, high patient-to-nurse ratios, and limited continuing professional development.⁷ In Nigeria, several single-centre studies have reported moderate satisfaction with nursing care, but substantial variation exists across regions and facility types.⁸ For instance, work in tertiary hospitals in the south-western and north-central zones has highlighted both strengths in nurse courtesies and persistent weaknesses in information sharing and privacy protection.⁹ However, data from the north-eastern part of the country, particularly Bauchi State, remain scarce. Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare (FUHSTHA) is a relatively young tertiary institution serving a large catchment area, yet no published evidence exists on how its inpatients perceive nursing care. Understanding local satisfaction levels and the specific aspects of care that patients find most important is essential for targeted quality improvement.

The present study therefore aimed to assess patient satisfaction with nursing care at FUHSTHA, to evaluate patients' perceptions of nurses' attitudes, and to identify strategies that patients consider important for enhancing satisfaction.

Materials and methods

Study Design and Setting

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted at Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The hospital is a tertiary referral facility located along Sule Katagum Road in Azare. At the time of the study, it provided inpatient services through medical, surgical, maternity, and paediatric wards.

Population and Sampling

The target population comprised all patients admitted to the hospital wards for at least three days during the four-week data collection period (total N = 370). Patients who were critically ill, cognitively impaired, or unable to provide

informed consent were excluded. The sample size was determined using Yamane's formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{370}{1 + 370(0.05)^2} = 192$$

A convenience sampling method was used; all eligible patients available on the days of data collection were invited to participate until the required sample size was reached. All 192 approached patients completed the questionnaire, yielding a 100% response rate.

Instrument

Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire developed following a review of the relevant literature.^{1,4,8} The questionnaire had four sections:

- Section A: sociodemographic characteristics (sex, age, educational status, religion, marital status).
- Section B: nurses' attitude (8 items), rated on a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree).
- Section C: patient satisfaction with nursing care (8 items) on the same scale; two items were negatively worded and reverse-scored before analysis.
- Section D: strategies to improve patient satisfaction (8 items), also rated on a 4-point agreement scale; the first item was phrased negatively to avoid response acquiescence bias.

Validity and Reliability

Content validity was established through review by three experts in nursing science. A pilot test was conducted with 20 inpatients at a nearby general hospital who were not part of the main study. The test-retest reliability, assessed over a two-week interval, was $r = 0.78$, indicating acceptable stability. Following the pilot, ambiguous wording was corrected; the statement "Sometimes nurses make me wonderful" was clarified to "Sometimes I wonder whether the nursing care I receive is correct."

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining ethical clearance, data were collected over four weeks by trained research assistants. Participants were interviewed at the bedside in a private setting. Each interview lasted approximately 20 minutes.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into IBM SPSS Statistics version 29.0. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) were computed. Mean scores were interpreted using the following scale: 1.00–1.49 = very dissatisfied/strongly disagree; 1.50–2.49 = dissatisfied/disagree; 2.50–3.49 = moderately satisfied/neutral to agree; 3.50–4.00 = highly satisfied/strongly agree. Because the study was descriptive and did not aim to test causal hypotheses, no inferential statistics were performed.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare (Approval No: NHREC/FMCA/11/24). Written informed consent was obtained from each participant. Confidentiality was ensured by assigning codes to questionnaires and storing data securely.

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics

The sample comprised 192 respondents. The majority were female (56%), married (50%), and had secondary education (59%) (Table 1). The most common age group was 40–49 years (35%).

Perception of Nurses' Attitude

Table 2 displays the mean agreement scores for each item. The highest-rated item was "Nurses treat patients with high regard and respect" (mean = 3.78). The aggregated mean of 3.39 indicates that patients perceived nurses' attitude positively overall.

Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care

The mean satisfaction scores are presented in Table 3. The item "When nurses provide care they are careful to check everything" received the highest mean (3.49), while the negatively worded item "I have some doubts about the ability of the nurses" had a mean of 1.83 after reverse-scoring, indicating little doubt. The overall satisfaction aggregate mean was 2.90, signifying moderate satisfaction.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants (N=192)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	85	44.3
	Female	107	55.7
Age group (years)	18–29	42	21.9
	30–39	60	31.3
	40–49	67	34.9
	50–59	23	12.0
Educational qualification	Secondary	113	58.9
	Diploma	69	35.9
	Degree	10	5.2
Religion	Islam	138	71.9
	Christianity	54	28.1
Marital status	Single	61	31.8
	Married	96	50.0
	Divorced	27	14.1
	Widowed	8	4.2

Table 2: Patients' perception of nurses' attitude (n=192)

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Nurses treat patients with high regard and respect	107	42	23	20	3.78
Nurses explain my condition/illness in a way I can understand	101	67	21	3	3.38
Nurses explain procedures clearly before performing them	112	60	13	7	3.44
Nurses involve my family in decisions and care	90	83	10	9	3.32
Nurses seek my permission before performing any procedure	100	70	12	10	3.35
Nurses respect my privacy by not exposing my body to others	106	77	5	4	3.48
Nurses keep my health information confidential	70	81	33	8	3.11
Nurses allow me to make decisions about whether to accept or reject treatment	84	90	7	11	3.28
Aggregate mean					3.39

SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree

Table 3: Patient satisfaction with nursing care (n=192)

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
The nursing care I have been receiving is just about perfect	81	94	7	10	3.28
I am dissatisfied with some aspects of the nursing care I received (R)	6	10	115	61	3.21
I think nurses have everything needed to provide complete nursing care	82	54	30	26	3.00
Sometimes I wonder whether the nursing care I receive is correct (R)	100	47	25	20	3.18
When nurses provide care they are careful to check everything when treating and examining me	109	74	4	5	3.49
I have some doubts about the ability of the nurses providing my care (R)	9	20	94	69	3.17
Nurses treat me in a very friendly and courteous manner	111	50	25	6	3.38
Nurses are good about explaining the reason for nursing care	122	27	23	20	3.30
Aggregate mean					2.90

Items marked (R) were negatively worded and reverse-scored; the mean reported is after reversal.

Strategies to Improve Patient Satisfaction

Patients rated the importance of several improvement strategies (Table 4). “Timely administration of medication” and “having enough nurses” were the most strongly endorsed strategies (means 3.41 and 3.28, respectively). The negatively worded item “Effective communication between nurses and patients is

not important for satisfaction” obtained a mean of 1.61, indicating that patients strongly disagree with that statement and therefore consider communication very important. No aggregate mean was computed because one item was negatively worded, making an unweighted average inappropriate.

Table 4: Patients’ views on strategies to improve satisfaction (n=192)

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Timely administration of medication improves patient satisfaction	105	66	17	4	3.41
Having enough nurses improves patient satisfaction	103	50	30	9	3.28
Providing useful information about my condition does not improve my satisfaction (R)	43	54	53	42	2.50*
Involving patients in their care improves satisfaction	90	60	20	22	3.13
Spending adequate time with patients improves satisfaction	95	55	22	20	3.17
Providing privacy when performing nursing care is not of great importance (R)	102	40	39	11	2.21*
Completing all nursing procedures improves satisfaction	12	35	70	75	1.91
*Effective communication between nurses and patients is not important for satisfaction (R)	11	20	45	116	1.61

Items marked (R) were negatively worded; mean values reflect raw agreement without reversal. Interpretation: for these negative items, a low mean indicates strong disagreement, i.e., patients believe the opposite (e.g., communication is important).

Discussion

This study found that patients at FUHSTA perceived nurses’ attitudes positively, with an aggregate mean of 3.39 on items relating to respect, communication, and confidentiality. These perceptions are consistent with findings from other Nigerian tertiary hospitals, in which nurse courtesy is frequently rated highly.^{8,9}

Overall patient satisfaction, however, was only moderate (mean 2.90). This aligns with reports from similar settings where structural constraints, such as high workload and inadequate material resources, dampen satisfaction despite positive interpersonal interactions.⁷ The items with the lowest means concerned doubts about nurses’ ability and dissatisfaction with some aspects of care, though after reverse-scoring the level of doubt

was low. Notably, the item “I think nurses have everything needed to provide complete nursing care” received a moderate score (3.00), suggesting that patients perceive resource gaps that may limit optimal care.

Regarding improvement strategies, patients strongly endorsed the importance of adequate staffing and timely medication administration. This finding echoes the global evidence linking nurse staffing levels to patient satisfaction.⁶ The strong disagreement with the statement that communication is not important (mean 1.61) reinforces, indirectly, the high value patients place on effective communication, even though the present descriptive design did not test statistical associations between communication and satisfaction.

Strengths and limitations

The study provides the first published data on patient satisfaction with nursing care in this institution, offering a baseline for quality-improvement initiatives. However, several limitations must be acknowledged. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference. Convenience sampling may have introduced selection bias, as patients who were more accessible or agreeable could be overrepresented. All data were collected at a single site, limiting generalisability to other hospitals. Additionally, the use of a self-developed questionnaire, although validated, means that comparability with other studies that used different instruments may be imperfect. Finally, no inferential statistics were performed, so the relationships between sociodemographic factors or specific attitudes and overall satisfaction were not examined. Future studies should employ probability sampling and include multivariable analysis to identify independent predictors of satisfaction.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that inpatients at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, were moderately satisfied with the nursing care they received. Nurses' attitudes were generally rated positively, but satisfaction scores point to clear opportunities for improvement. Based on patients' feedback, priorities for enhancing satisfaction include ensuring timely medication administration, increasing nurse staffing, strengthening communication, and more actively involving patients in their own care. Hospital management should integrate regular patient satisfaction surveys into the institution's quality assurance framework so that service improvements are driven by evidence rather than assumptions.

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